

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL MATURITY AND CLASSROOM ENVIRONMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

Education

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ABSTRACT

The paper discussed classroom environment as a major determining factor for emotional maturity. The investigator selected 300 XI and XII students from 10 higher secondary schools of Sivagiri Taluk. For selecting the students, the investigator used random sampling method. The investigator used survey method of research to study the relationship between emotional maturity and classroom environment of higher secondary students. The higher secondary students were provided with two questionnaires of Classroom Environment Scale by Manikanda prabhu (2015) and Emotional Maturity Scale by Yasvir singh and Magesh Bharagava (1990). It was null hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between emotional maturity and classroom environment of higher secondary students. The collected data were subjected to Pearson product moment correlation. The findings rejected the null hypotheses. The results showed that there is significant relationship between emotional maturity and classroom environment of higher secondary students.

KEYWORDS:

classroom environment, emotional maturity, higher secondary students, random sampling method, Pearson product moment correlation

INTRODUCTION

Human beings are creatures of feelings or emotions. Our emotions control our behavior. Emotions are one of the dimensions of personal experience. They are expressed as love, fear, anger, laughter, tears etc. They involve feelings of jubilation or depression. If there had been no emotions in the life of the organism, our life would have been devoid of aspiration. (Journal-Meston college of Education, 2006: vol5) According to Arthur. T. Jersild describes, "An adequate description of emotional maturity must take account of full scope of the individuals capacity and powers, and of his ability to use and enjoy them. In its broadest sense emotional maturity means the degree to which the person has realized his potential for richness of living and has developed his capacity to enjoy things, to relate himself to others to love and to laugh, his capacity for whole hearted sorrow when an occasion for grief arises, and his capacity to show fear when there is occasion to be frightened, without feeling a need to use a false mask of courage." (G.Aruna Mohan, 2006: 180)

Amborse *et. al.* (2010) define classroom environment as "the intellectual, social, emotional, and physical environments in which our students learn. Climate is determined by a constellation of interacting factors that include faculty-student interaction, the tone instructors set, instances of stereotyping or tokenism, the course demographics (for example, relative size of racial and other social groups enrolled in the course), student-student interaction, and the range of perspectives represented in the course content and materials". Classroom climate is affected not only by blatant instances of inequality directed towards a person or group of people, but also by smaller, more subtle "micro-inequities" that can accumulate to have significant negative impacts on learning. A positive environment is one in which students feel a sense of belonging, trust others, and feel encouraged to tackle challenges, take risks, and ask questions (Bucholz & Sheffler, 2009). Such an environment provides relevant content, clear learning goals and feedback, opportunities to build social skills, and strategies to help students succeed

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

In the present circumstances, youth as well as children are facing difficulties in life. These difficulties are giving rise to many psychosomatic problems such as anxiety, tensions, frustrations and emotional upsets in day to day life. So, the study of emotional life is now emerging as a descriptive science, comparable with anatomy. It deals with interplay of forces with intensities and quantities. Emotional maturity is not only the effective determinant of personality pattern, but is also helps to control the growth of adolescents' development. The concept 'Mature' emotional behavior of any level is that which reflects the fruits of normal emotional development. A person who is able to keep his emotions under control, which is able to

break delay and to suffer without self pity, might still be emotionally stunned and childish. No one is born with emotional maturity; it is shaped by our relationship with and upbringing by our parents, and life experiences. Parents raise mature children by validating, mirroring, loving and accepting their children. Parents who have achieved personal fulfillment and their own emotional maturity tend to raise mature children. An emotionally mature adult grows from a childhood where one successfully struggles with failures, disappointments, and heartaches. Child should be starting to deal with his or her feelings in an age-appropriate way. In order to be emotionally ready for school, a child should not be too fearful, anxious, or tense. Parents can help children to think about things, talk about what might happen, help them to slow down, model discussion of choices, show them how to make simple decisions, and can use logical and natural consequences to teach children about cause and effect and actions and reactions. "There are meaningful gaps in adults understanding of when children between the ages of birth and six achieve physical, cognitive, social and emotional milestones." Parents need to know what is typical development in the area of emotional maturity, so that they will have reasonable, age-appropriate expectations of their children and can guide them appropriately. This will help a child to enjoy learning and playing with others, to explore new opportunities, and to be able to take advantage of the many learning experiences offered at school. Emotional maturity does not crucify emotions – it controls and guides them with right knowledge and true wisdom. Emotional maturity develops hand in hand with physical, mental and spiritual growth – the four blending, finally, into the perfect spiritual destiny and the very purpose of life. It can bring very great and rewarding and lasting happiness. Middle schools must provide opportunities for students to see that a wide range of emotions is normal. Learning to balance negative emotions with thoughts and actions that create positive emotions is a lifelong task. Neglect of the emotional lives of children impacts on their intellectual lives and achievements as emotions are critical to the learning process and to the full development of the individual and to society. Teachers in the schools are in the best position to help children to alleviate their fears, frustrations, sadness and self – doubt by teaching them to use their prodigious intellectual abilities to support their emotional richness. With this background, the investigator entitled the study as "Emotional Maturity and Classroom Environment of Higher Secondary Students"

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To find out whether there is any significant relationship between emotional maturity and classroom environment of higher secondary students.

METHODOLOGY

The investigator used survey method of research to study the

relationship between emotional maturity and classroom environment of higher secondary students.

POPULATION

The population of the present study were all the students studying standard XI and XII in the higher secondary schools of Sivagiri Taluk.

SAMPLE

The investigator selected 300 XI and XII students from 10 higher secondary schools of Sivagiri Taluk. For selecting the students, the investigator used random sampling method.

TOOLS USED

The higher secondary students were provided with two questionnaires of Classroom Environment Scale by Manikanda prabhu (2015) and Emotional Maturity Scale by Yasvir singh and Magesh Bharagava (1990).

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

The collected data were subjected to Pearson product moment correlation.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

There is no significant relationship between emotional maturity and classroom environment of higher secondary students.

Table-1
Relationship between emotional maturity and classroom environment of higher secondary students

Variable	Count	Calculated 'r' value	Table 'r' value	Remarks at 0.01 level
Emotional maturity and Classroom environment	300	0.171	0.149	S

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated r-value (0.171) is greater than the table r-value(0.149) for $df=298$ the table value at 1% level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant relationship between emotional maturity and classroom environment of higher secondary students.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

From the results of Pearson Product Moment Correlation, the investigator found that there is significant relationship between emotional maturity and classroom environment of higher secondary students. The reason may be that schooling is an emotionally laden process for students, teachers and parents. Besides parents, the biggest influence on a children's socio-emotional development is the classroom environment. After all, children spend the majority of every day at school, so of course classroom environment will influence emotional maturity of high school students. Schools must create healthy learning communities that are physically, emotionally and intellectually safe, clean and secure. And the emotional domain is foundational to all other developmental domains. If children start school in an emotionally supportive environment, they will acquire the love of learning necessary for success in all areas of school.

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